

Simultaneous estimation of ramipril and metoprolol tartrate in combined dosage forms

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Manuscript received 12 October 2006, accepted 3 April 2007

Abstract : Four new analytical methods were developed based on the simultaneous estimation of drugs in a binary mixture without prior separation. In simultaneous equation method, the drugs were determined by using the absorbance values of ramipril and metoprolol at selected wavelengths, viz. 205 nm and 222.5 nm respectively. The second method depends on the application of area under the curve at selected wavelength range, 200 to 210 nm and 217.5 to 227.5 nm for ramipril and metoprolol tartrate respectively, the linearity range for both the drugs were 10–20 µg/ml. Third method is based on the determination of graphical absorbance ratio at two selected wavelengths; one being the isoabsorptive point for the drugs (216.5 nm) and the other being the absorption maximum of metoprolol (222.5 nm), in this method both the drugs obeyed the Beer-Lambert's law in the concentration range of 16–24 µg/ml. The fourth method is based on the derivative spectrophotometric method at zero crossing wavelengths. These methods are simple, accurate, and rapid, and they require no preliminary separation and can therefore be used for routine analysis of both drugs in quality control laboratories.

Keywords : Ramipril, metoprolol.

Metoprolol is a beta-adrenergic antagonist used as an anti hypertensive drug. Methods for the quantitative estimation of metoprolol have been reported¹. Ramipril is a long acting angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitor used as an anti hypertensive drug and its estimation in pharmaceutical dosage forms have been reported². Although ramipril and metoprolol are commonly used in dual drug therapy as a potent anti hypertensive drug, yet no method is so far reported for their simultaneous estimation. A successful attempt has been made to estimate these two drugs simultaneously by spectrophotometric analysis.

Results and discussion

In the first method, the content of ramipril and metoprolol was directly found from the eqs. (1) and (2). In the second method the areas under the curve were measured in the range of 200–210 nm and 217.5–227.5 nm and the absorption coefficient values were determined, and were substituted in the eqs. (3) and (4) to give the results. In the third method, the absorbance ratio and the absorption coefficients were determined and the values were substituted in the eq. (5) to obtain the results. In the fourth method, the absorbance of one of the drugs was

taken at the zero crossing point of the other drug and the values were substituted in the eqs. (6) and (7). The precision, reproducibility, repeatability and accuracy of these methods were found to be good (Table 1). To test the accuracy and reproducibility of the proposed methods, recovery experiments were performed by adding known amount of the drugs to the preanalyzed formulations and reanalyzing the mixture by the proposed methods (Table 2). The percent recovery obtained indicates non-interference from the excipients like starch, magnesium stearate etc. if used in the formulations.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Shimadzu 1700 Pharmaspec UV-visible spectrophotometer with a matched pair of 10 mm quartz cells was used. The chemicals used were of analytical grade. The commercially available tablets of ramipril and metoprolol tartrate were procured from local market. Ramipril, received as gift sample from Cipla Labs., Mumbai and metoprolol from Novartis India Ltd., Mumbai, were used as such without further purification.

Solutions of ramipril and metoprolol tartrate were

Table 1. Results of analysis of commercial formulations

Method	Tablet brand	Tablet composition	Label claim ^a (mg/tab)	% Recovery (mg/tab)	Error in estimation	Percentage range of error with in 95% confidence limit ^a
I	A	Metoprolol	25	98.96 ± 0.103	0.0042	±0.0082
		Ramipril	2.5	99.05 ± 0.014	0.0059	±0.0115
	B	Metoprolol	25	98.96 ± 0.103	0.0067	±0.0096
		Ramipril	2.5	99.05 ± 0.014	0.0098	±0.0087
II	A	Metoprolol	25	99.25 ± 0.074	0.0303	±0.0594
		Ramipril	2.5	99.02 ± 0.139	0.0567	±0.1112
	B	Metoprolol	25	98.82 ± 0.232	0.0517	±0.2367
		Ramipril	2.5	99.12 ± 0.154	0.0239	±0.1542
III	A	Metoprolol	25	99.96 ± 0.010	0.0044	±0.0088
		Ramipril	2.5	99.56 ± 0.034	0.0026	±0.0104
	B	Metoprolol	25	99.37 ± 0.012	0.0080	±0.0163
		Ramipril	2.5	99.87 ± 0.027	0.0054	±0.0125
IV	A	Metoprolol	25	99.46 ± 0.010	0.0004	±0.0008
		Ramipril	2.5	99.57 ± 0.005	0.0002	±0.0004
	B	Metoprolol	25	99.27 ± 0.020	0.0006	±0.0012
		Ramipril	2.5	99.77 ± 0.013	0.0009	±0.0021

^aAverage of nine determinations.

prepared by dissolving accurately weighed 100 mg each of standard ramipril and standard metoprolol tartrate in 100 ml 0.1 N HCl separately. Working standard solutions (A) and (B) were further prepared by taking 1 ml of stock solution of ramipril and metoprolol tartrate in 10 ml volumetric flasks and made up the volume with 0.1 N HCl.

Methods of analysis :

Method I : Based on simultaneous equation method : Ramipril shows absorption maxima at 205 nm and metoprolol tartrate shows at 222.5 nm. The calibration curves for ramipril and metoprolol tartrate were prepared in the concentration range of 2–16 µg/ml and 8–20 µg/ml respectively at both the wavelengths i.e. 205 nm and 222.5 nm. The absorption coefficients were determined for both the drugs at both the wavelengths and following equations were obtained :

$$A_1 = 278.64C_{\text{metoprolol}} + 92.55C_{\text{ramipril}} \quad (\text{at } \lambda_{222.5}) \quad (1)$$

$$A_2 = 204.30C_{\text{metoprolol}} + 358.30C_{\text{ramipril}} \quad (\text{at } \lambda_{205}) \quad (2)$$

A_1 and A_2 are absorbances at 222.5 nm and 205 nm respectively and $C_{\text{metoprolol}}$ and C_{ramipril} are concentrations of metoprolol and ramipril respectively. The concentrations

of both the drugs in the mixture were determined by eqs. (1) and (2).

Method II : Area under the curve method : From the spectra, the areas under the curve were measured in the range of 217.5–227.5 nm and 200–210 nm. The absorption coefficients were determined for both the drugs at both the wavelength range and following equations were obtained.

$$A_1 = 2727.72C_{\text{metoprolol}} + 1560.73C_{\text{ramipril}} \quad (\text{at } \lambda_{227.5-217.5}) \quad (3)$$

$$A_2 = 2659.78C_{\text{metoprolol}} + 4196.05C_{\text{ramipril}} \quad (\text{at } \lambda_{200-210}) \quad (4)$$

where A_1 and A_2 are the areas under the curve of sample solution at the wavelength range 227.5–217.5 nm and 200–210 nm respectively and $C_{\text{metoprolol}}$ and C_{ramipril} are concentrations of metoprolol and ramipril respectively. The concentrations of both the drugs in the mixture were determined by eqs. (3) and (4).

Method III : Graphical absorbance ratio method : This method is based on the method used by Ghanem *et al.* which makes use of the iso-absorptive point of the two drugs i.e. the wavelength of equal absorptivity of the two components of the mixture. The iso-absorptive point was 216.5 nm in this case. The other wavelength selected is

Table 2. Drug recovery study

Method	Tablet brand	Metoprolol tartrate		Ramipril	
		Percent recovery ^a	Standard deviation ^a	Percent recovery ^a	Standard deviation ^a
I	A	98.84	0.0053	99.01	0.0040
	B	98.36	0.0064	98.96	0.0043
II	A	99.04	0.0482	99.21	0.0937
	B	99.32	0.0367	99.14	0.0879
III	A	99.89	0.0019	99.69	0.0036
	B	99.67	0.0065	99.82	0.0049
IV	A	99.94	0.0019	99.97	0.0007
	B	99.91	0.0024	99.65	0.0019

^aReadings are average of nine determinations.

the absorption maximum of one of the components. In this case it was 222.5 nm, the absorption maximum of metoprolol tartrate. The concentrations of the two components are related to the ratio of the absorbances at these two wavelengths. The absorbance of the mixture was noted at 216.5 and 222.5 nm. Calibration curves of metoprolol and ramipril were plotted in the concentration range 16–24 µg/ml (range for which Beer-Lambert's law followed). The absorption coefficients were determined for both the drugs and the average value was taken. These values and the absorbance ratio were used to develop equations as given below.

$$A_1 = 225.99 (C_x + C_y) \\ = 225.99C_x (0.8305/Q_m - 0.3995) \quad (5)$$

where $Q_m = A_2/A_1$ and A_1, A_2 are the absorbances at 216.5 and 222.5 nm respectively. C_x and C_y are concentrations of metoprolol tartrate and ramipril respectively.

Method IV : Derivative spectrophotometric method : Upon examining the first-derivative spectra of the two drugs, it can be noticed that metoprolol tartrate can be determined at 205 nm where ramipril has no contribution and ramipril can be determined at 222.5 nm where metoprolol tartrate shows a zero crossing.

$$A = -0.0015C + 0.0059 \quad r = 0.9944 \\ (\lambda = 205 \text{ nm}) \quad (6)$$

$$A = -0.0014C + 0.0015 \quad r = 0.9971 \\ (\lambda = 222.5 \text{ nm}) \quad (7)$$

where C is the concentration in µg/mL, A is the peak amplitude of the first-derivative curves at 222.5 and 205 nm for ramipril and metoprolol tartrate respectively and r is the correlation coefficient.

Estimation from tablets : Twenty tablets were weighed and average weight determined. Powder equivalent to 25 mg of metoprolol tartrate and 2.5 mg ramipril was extracted quantitatively with small amount of methanol. Insoluble excipients were separated by filtration. The supernatant liquid was transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up with 0.1 N HCl. The solution so obtained was suitably diluted with 0.1 N HCl so that the concentration can be read directly from the calibration curve, and the absorbances were taken at different wavelengths as stated above. Using the eqs. (1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6) and (7) the concentrations were determined (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

Thanks are extended to the Director, Institute of Pharmacy, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur (C.G.) for providing necessary facilities for research work and AICTE, New Delhi for financial assistance under the scheme RPS. We are also grateful to Cipla Labs., Mumbai and Novartis India Ltd., Mumbai for providing gift samples of ramipril and metoprolol tartrate.

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